

Synthesis and screening for antibacterial, analgesic and anti-inflammatory activity of Mannich bases derived from 1*H*-indole-2,3-dione

V. J. Patro^a, C. S. Panda^b, B. M. Sahoo^a, N. K. Mishra^a and J. R. Panda^{a*}

^aDepartment of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Roland Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Berhampur-760 010, Orissa, India

E-mail : jrpanda77@gmail.com

^bDepartment of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Indira Gandhi Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Bhubaneswar, Orissa, India

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Abstract : The reaction of isatin (1*H*-indole-2,3-dione) with substituted anilines in presence of acetic acid produces Schiff bases. Reaction of the Schiff bases with different secondary amines in presence of formaldehyde yields Mannich bases. The synthesized Mannich bases were screened for their antibacterial, analgesic and anti-inflammatory activities by the standard methods. The structures of the compounds were confirmed by means of physical and spectral data.

Keywords : Schiff bases, Mannich bases, antibacterial, analgesic, anti-inflammatory.

Introduction

Schiff and Mannich bases of isatin represent one of the important classes of organic compounds because of their broad spectrum of pharmacological activities such as antibacterial¹⁻⁵, antifungal⁶⁻⁹, antiviral¹⁰⁻¹², anti-HIV¹³⁻¹⁵, antiprotozoal^{16,17}, antihelmintic^{18,19}, antidepressant²⁰, anti-inflammatory²¹, analgesic²² and anticonvulsant²³ activities. The good biological profile of isatin derivatives prompted us to synthesize some Mannich bases of isatin. In the present study, aromatic primary amines were subjected to reaction with isatin to form Schiff bases. The corresponding *N*-Mannich bases were synthesized by reacting them with different secondary amines and formaldehyde. The chemical structures of the synthesized compounds were confirmed by means of their physical, IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectral data. The synthesized compounds were tested for their antibacterial activity by cup plate method, analgesic activity by acetic acid induced writhing response, hot plate reaction time and tail immersion method and anti-inflammatory activity by carrageenan induced paw edema method.

Results and discussion

Reaction of isatin with substituted anilines in presence

of acetic acid under reflux condition produces Schiff bases. The reaction of the Schiff bases with different secondary amines in presence of formaldehyde yields Mannich bases (1-10) (Scheme 1). The IR spectrum of the compounds showed characteristic peaks at 1716-1732 (C=O), 1600-1616 (C=N) and 1454-1469 cm⁻¹ (C=C). ¹H NMR spectrum of the compounds showed signals at δ 3.32-5.13 (2H, s, CH₂) and the aromatic protons showed signals at δ 6.33-8.15 (m, ArH). The mass spectrum of the compounds was good agreement with their molecular ion peaks. The physical data of the synthesized compounds are given in Table 1.

The synthesized compounds were evaluated *in vitro* for antibacterial activity by cup plate method. The results are summarized in Table 2 including the activity of the standard. The compound 5 exhibited highest activity against all the tested organisms. It has also been observed that the compound 2 showed highest activity against *S. epidermidis* and *S. aureus*. But the activity was less than that of the standard drug Tetracycline.

The analgesic activity of the synthesized compounds was evaluated using both chemical and thermal methods. Acetic acid induced writhing test used for detecting both central and peripheral analgesia, whereas hot plate and

Scheme 1

Table 1. Physical properties of the synthesized Mannich bases

Compd.	R	R ¹	Molecular formula	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	R _f
1	Phenyl	Piperidino	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₃ O	138-139	73	0.512
2	2-Nitrophenyl	Piperidino	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₃	110-111	70	0.477
3	3-Nitrophenyl	Piperidino	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₃	154-155	67	0.567
4	Phenyl	Morpholino	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂	144-145	63	0.542
5	4-Chlorophenyl	Morpholino	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ ClN ₃ O ₂	140-141	69	0.636
6	3-Chloro-4-fluorophenyl	Morpholino	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ ClFN ₃ O ₂	129-130	71	0.565
7	2-Nitrophenyl	Diethylamino	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₃	170-171	77	0.469
8	3-Chlorophenyl	Diethylamino	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ ClN ₃ O	157-158	72	0.656
9	3-Nitrophenyl	Diphenylamino	C ₂₇ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₃	241-242	65	0.811
10	4-Bromophenyl	Diphenylamino	C ₂₇ H ₂₀ BrN ₃ O	255-256	62	0.771

Solvent system : Benzene : Chloroform (55 : 45).

Table 2. Antibacterial activity of the synthesized compounds (1-10)

Compd.	Diameter of zone of inhibition (mm)				
	<i>P. vulgaris</i> MTCC-426	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> MTCC-424	<i>E. coli</i> MTCC-40	<i>S. aureus</i> MTCC-87	<i>S. epidermidis</i> MTCC-2639
1	13.66 ± 0.57 ^a	15.66 ± 0.57	16.33 ± 0.57	10.66 ± 0.57	11.66 ± 0.57
2	16.00 ± 1.00	11.66 ± 0.57	12.00 ± 1.00	18.66 ± 0.57	21.00 ± 1.00
3	15.00 ± 1.00	13.33 ± 0.57	15.33 ± 0.57	16.33 ± 1.52	14.00 ± 1.00
4	13.33 ± 0.57	15.00 ± 1.00	13.00 ± 1.00	13.33 ± 0.57	11.66 ± 0.57
5	20.33 ± 0.57	20.00 ± 1.00	22.00 ± 1.00	19.33 ± 0.57	16.33 ± 0.57
6	11.33 ± 0.57	14.00 ± 1.00	13.33 ± 0.57	16.33 ± 0.57	11.66 ± 0.57
7	14.33 ± 0.57	14.33 ± 0.57	13.33 ± 0.57	16.33 ± 0.57	15.33 ± 0.57
8	18.66 ± 0.57	10.33 ± 0.57	13.33 ± 0.57	12.33 ± 0.57	10.66 ± 1.52
9	15.00 ± 1.00	9.00 ± 1.00	16.33 ± 1.52	12.00 ± 1.00	9.33 ± 0.57
10	10.00 ± 1.00	9.00 ± 1.00	7.66 ± 0.57	-	-
Tetracycline	23.00 ± 1.00	21.33 ± 0.57	31.33 ± 0.57	21.66 ± 0.57	23.00 ± 1.00

^aResults were expressed as mean ± S.D. (n = 3).

tail immersion methods are considered to be selective for the drugs acting centrally. In acetic acid induced writhing test, the compounds 5 and 8 were found to be significant ($p < 0.001$) in reducing the number of wriths. The com-

pounds 1, 4, 6 and 7 were also found significant ($p < 0.05$) in reducing the number of wriths. The standard drug, Indomethacin was found to be more potent than the test compounds (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Results were expressed as mean \pm SEM ($n = 6$) * $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.001$ compared to control.

With respect to the hot plate test, the compounds 1, 2, 3, 4 ($p < 0.05$) and 8 ($p < 0.01$) were found to be significant only in the first hour, whereas the compound 5 was found to be significant both in the first ($p < 0.001$) and the second hour ($p < 0.05$) of the study. None of the compounds has significant activity in all the three hours of the study except the standard, Pentazocine ($p < 0.001$) (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Results were expressed as mean \pm SEM ($n = 6$) * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$ compared to control.

In the tail immersion test, the compounds 4 and 7 were found to be significant ($p < 0.01$ and $p < 0.05$ respectively) in increasing the latency only in the first hour of the study, whereas compound 5 ($p < 0.01$ and p

< 0.05), compound 8 ($p < 0.05$) and the standard, Pentazocine ($p < 0.001$) were found to be significant in both first and the second hour of the study (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Results were expressed as mean \pm SEM ($n = 6$) * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$ compared to control.

The result of Carrageenan induced paw edema method shows that some of the synthesized compounds have significant anti-inflammatory activity. Among these, the compound 5 showed significant ($p < 0.001$) anti-inflammatory activity at the third, fourth and fifth hour, whereas it was found to be non-significant at the first and the second hour. Similarly, the compounds 3 and 4 showed significant ($p < 0.05$) activity at the fourth and the fifth hour and were non-significant at the first, second and third hour. The compounds 6 and 7 have significant ($p < 0.05$) activity at the fourth hour only (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Results were expressed as mean \pm SEM ($n = 6$) * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$ compared to control.

Experimental

All the melting points were determined in open capillaries, expressed in °C and are uncorrected. The IR spectra of the compounds were recorded on Shimadzu IR Affinity series-1 in KBr and the values are expressed in cm^{-1} . The ^1H NMR spectra of the compounds were recorded on a Bruker Advance II 400 MHz spectrophotometer and the values are expressed in δ ppm. The mass spectra of the compounds were recorded on Micromass Q-ToF Micro; in m/z . The purity of the compounds was checked by thin layer chromatography on silica gel G coated plates.

Synthesis of Schiff bases of isatin : Equimolar (0.01 mol) quantity of isatin and substituted anilines were dissolved in sufficient amount of ethanol and refluxed for 3 h in presence of glacial acetic acid. After standing for approximately 24 h at room temperature, the products were separated by filtration, dried under vacuum and recrystallized from warm ethanol.

Synthesis of Mannich bases of isatin : Equimolar quantity of secondary amines (0.004 mol) in 10 ml of ethanol was added to slurry containing appropriate Schiff bases and formaldehyde solution (37% v/v) in 10 ml of ethanol. The reaction mixture was stirred for 2 h at room temperature and kept under refrigeration for 48 h. The products were separated by suction filtration, dried under vacuum and recrystallized from ethanol. TLC was monitored by using solvent system benzene : chloroform (55 : 45) and the spots were identified by placing the plate in iodine chamber.

Antibacterial activity :

The synthesized compounds were screened *in vitro* for their antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* (MTCC-87), *Escherichia coli* (MTCC-40), *Staphylococcus epidermidis* (MTCC-2639), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (MTCC-424) and *Proteus vulgaris* (MTCC-426) using cup plate method²⁴. The compounds were tested at 500 μg concentration in DMSO, using nutrient agar as the medium. After 24 h of incubation at 37 °C, the zone of inhibition formed were measured in mm against standard drug Tetracycline and the data were presented in Table 2.

Analgesic activity :

The analgesic activity of the synthesized compounds

was studied using acetic acid induced writhing response²⁵, hot plate reaction time²⁶ and tail immersion method²⁷.

In the three models, acetic acid induced writhing response (chemical method), hot plate reaction time and tail immersion method (thermal method), the animals were divided into different groups ($n = 6$). Group I served as control (1% carboxy methyl cellulose as vehicle, 1 ml/kg, p.o.), group II served as standard (Indomethacin, 10 mg/kg, p.o. in acetic acid induced writhing method and Pentazocine, 10 mg/kg, p.o. in hot plate and tail immersion methods) and other groups were served as test groups and received the test compounds each at the dose of 200 mg/kg/p.o. The vehicle, standard and test compounds were administered in the suspension form in carboxy methyl cellulose to the respective groups, 30 min before the induction of pain, either by acetic acid or by thermal stimuli.

Acetic acid induced writhing method : Healthy Swiss albino mice (20–30 g) were placed into individual restraining cages. The animals were then allowed to adapt in the cages for 30 min before testing. Writhing was induced in mice by administration of 0.6% acetic acid (10 ml/kg body weight, i.p.). The numbers of writhes were calculated over the period of 20 min after acetic acid injection. A writh is indicated by an abdominal constriction followed by full extension of hind limb.

Hot plate method : The hot plate test in mice was performed by using Eddy's hot plate (INCO) maintained at a temperature of 55 ± 1 °C. The animals which showed fore paw licking or jumping response within 6–8 s were selected for the study. The animals were individually exposed to the hot plate maintained at 55 ± 1 °C. A cut off period of 15 s was observed to avoid damage to the paw. The time taken in sec for fore or hind paw licking or jumping was taken as reaction time.

Tail immersion method : Healthy Wistar rats (150–200 g) were placed into individual restraining cages leaving the tail hanging out freely. The animals were then allowed to adapt in the cages for 30 min before testing. The lower 5 cm portion of the tail was marked and immersed in a cup of freshly filled water of 55 °C. Within a few seconds the rat reacts by withdrawing the tail. The reaction time was recorded by a stop watch. After each attempt the tail was carefully dried. The reaction was determined before oral feeding of the drug and the test compounds which was recorded as zero minutes reading.

After the drug administration the reaction time was recorded at 1st hour and 2nd hour. The mean reaction time was recorded for each group and compared with the control.

Anti-inflammatory activity :

Carrageenan induced paw edema method : The anti-inflammatory activity was determined by carrageenan induced paw edema method^{28,29} in Wistar rats by using digital plethysmometer (Panlab LE 7500). Wistar rats of either sex (180–250 g) were selected and housed under standard laboratory conditions, given standard rat pellet and tap water ad libitum and maintained under standard environmental conditions throughout the period of experimentation. They had free access to standard diet and water. The animals were divided into different groups of six animals each ($n = 6$) and fasted for 12 h before the experiment. Group I served as control and received vehicle, group II served as standard group and received Indomethacin (10 mg/kg, p.o.) and other groups were served as test groups and received the test compounds (200 mg/kg/p.o.) one hour prior to carrageenan injection. The vehicle, standard and test compounds were administered in the suspension form in carboxy methyl cellulose to the respective groups. The initial right hind paw volume of the rats were measured using a digital plethysmometer and then 0.1 ml of 1% w/v carrageenan solution in normal saline was injected into the sub planter region of the right hind paw. The volume of right hind paw was measured at 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th and 5th hour after carrageenan injection by using digital plethysmometer. The data were expressed as paw volume (ml).

Compound 1 : IR (KBr) (cm^{-1}) : 1724 (C=O), 1602 (C=N), 1458 (C=C); $^1\text{H NMR } \delta$ (ppm) : 1.10–1.22 (6H, m, CH_2 piperidinyl), 2.50–2.51 (4H, m, CH_2 piperidinyl), 3.5 (2H, s, CH_2), 6.33–7.54 (9H, m, ArH) (Found : C, 75.23; H, 6.67; N, 13.14. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_3\text{O}$: C, 75.21; H, 6.63; N, 13.16%).

Compound 2 : IR (cm^{-1}) : 1732 (C=O), 1612 (C=N), 1469 (C=C), 1544 and 1350 (NO_2); $^1\text{H NMR } \delta$ (ppm) : 1.16–1.31 (6H, m, CH_2 piperidinyl), 2.58–2.59 (4H, m, CH_2 piperidinyl), 3.33 (2H, s, CH_2), 6.57–7.74 (8H, m, ArH); Mass (m/z) : 365 (Found : C, 65.88; H, 5.56; N, 15.42. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4\text{O}_3$: C, 65.92; H, 5.53; N, 15.38%).

Compound 3 : IR (cm^{-1}) : 1718 (C=O), 1616 (C=N), 1456 (C=C), 1529 and 1352 (NO_2); $^1\text{H NMR } \delta$ (ppm) : 1.14–1.26 (6H, m, CH_2 piperidinyl), 2.50–2.52 (4H, m, CH_2 piperidinyl), 3.53 (2H, s, CH_2), 6.59–7.64 (8H, m, ArH); Mass (m/z) : 365 (Found : C, 65.95; H, 5.57; N, 15.39. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4\text{O}_3$: C, 65.92; H, 5.53; N, 15.38%).

Compound 4 : IR (cm^{-1}) : 1716 (C=O), 1610 (C=N), 1458 (C=C), 1123 (C–O–C); $^1\text{H NMR } \delta$ (ppm) : 5.13 (2H, s, CH_2), 2.58–2.61 (4H, m, CH_2 morpholinyl), 3.03–3.33 (4H, m, CH_2 morpholinyl), 6.57–7.74 (9H, m, Ar-H); Mass (m/z) : 360 (Found : C, 71.05; H, 5.99; N, 13.06. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2$: C, 71.01; H, 5.96; N, 13.08%).

Compound 5 : IR (cm^{-1}) : 1716 (C=O), 1608 (C=N), 1454 (C=C), 1170 (C–O–C), 709 (C–Cl); $^1\text{H NMR } \delta$ (ppm) : 4.44 (2H, s, CH_2), 2.50–2.60 (4H, m, CH_2 morpholinyl), 3.27–3.61 (4H, m, CH_2 morpholinyl), 6.47–7.56 (8H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 64.10; H, 5.07; N, 11.80. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{ClN}_3\text{O}_2$: C, 64.13; H, 5.10; N, 11.81%).

Compound 6 : IR (cm^{-1}) : 1716 (C=O), 1614 (C=N), 1456 (C=C), 1174 (C–O–C), 1055 (C–F), 723 (C–Cl); $^1\text{H NMR } \delta$ (ppm) : 3.32 (2H, s, CH_2), 2.57–2.59 (4H, m, CH_2 morpholinyl), 3.19–3.23 (4H, m, CH_2 morpholinyl), 6.55–7.76 (7H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 61.09; H, 4.61; N, 11.22. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{17}\text{ClFN}_3\text{O}_2$: C, 61.05; H, 4.58; N, 11.24%).

Compound 7 : IR (cm^{-1}) : 1726 (C=O), 1600 (C=N), 1467 (C=C), 1529 and 1354 (NO_2); $^1\text{H NMR } \delta$ (ppm) : 1.01–1.05 (6H, t, $\text{N}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3)_2$), 2.51–2.66 (4H, q, $\text{N}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3)_2$), 4.49 (2H, s, CH_2), 6.42–8.07 (8H, m, Ar-H); Mass (m/z) : 353 (Found : C, 64.80; H, 5.75; N, 15.93. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4\text{O}_3$: C, 64.76; H, 5.72; N, 15.90%).

Compound 8 : IR (cm^{-1}) : 1728 (C=O), 1602 (C=N), 1462 (C=C), 759 (C–Cl); $^1\text{H NMR } \delta$ (ppm) : 0.97–1.15 (6H, t, $\text{N}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3)_2$), 2.50–2.65 (4H, q, $\text{N}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3)_2$), 4.48 (2H, s, CH_2), 6.56–7.69 (8H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 66.74; H, 5.94; N, 12.31. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{20}\text{ClN}_3\text{O}$: C, 66.76; H, 5.90; N, 12.29%).

Compound 9 : IR (cm^{-1}) : 1716 (C=O), 1616 (C=N), 1529 and 1354 (NO_2), 1456 (C=C); $^1\text{H NMR } \delta$ (ppm) : 4.62 (2H, s, CH_2), 7.10–8.15 (18H, m, Ar-H); Mass (m/z) : 448 (Found : C, 72.37; H, 4.54; N, 12.47. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4\text{O}_3$: C, 72.31; H, 4.49; N, 12.49%).

Compound 10 : IR (cm⁻¹) : 1730 (C=O), 1606 (C=N), 582 (C-Br), 1462 (C=C); ¹H NMR δ (ppm) : 5.01 (2H, s, CH₂), 6.31-7.67 (18H, m, Ar-H); Mass (m/z) : 483 (Found : C, 67.20; H, 4.22; N, 8.73. Calcd. for C₂₇H₂₀BrN₃O : C, 67.23; H, 4.18; N, 8.71%).

Statistical analysis : The results of statistical analysis for animal experiments were expressed as mean ± SEM. The number of animals in each group were six (n = 6). All the results were statistically analyzed by two way ANOVA followed by Bonferroni post tests except that of acetic acid induced writhing model where the data were analyzed by one way ANOVA followed by Dunnet's multiple comparison test by using GraphPad Prism software, v 5.0 (trial) (GraphPad Inc, USA). *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001 compared to control were considered to be statistically significant.

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